

STUDENT PRISONERS' CHALLENGES FACED WITH SUPERVISORS DURING THEIR ACADEMIC STUDIES WHILE INCARCERATED: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the challenges faced by student prisoners in their academic studies, specifically focusing on the difficulties encountered in their relationships with academic supervisors. The purpose is to understand and document the unique obstacles these students face while pursuing education during incarceration. The research method involved tape-recorded interviews with a purposively selected sample of 12 student prisoners, chosen based on their active enrollment and pursuit of qualifications while incarcerated at a Namibian prison. A professional English transcriber transcribed the tape-recorded data verbatim. The transcriptions were then analysed by the author using an interpretive paradigm to interpret the information. The findings reveal significant challenges related to communication barriers due to prison restrictions, limited access to academic resources, delays in receiving feedback, insufficient support and mentorship, and administrative hurdles. By shedding light on these issues, the study aims to provide insights and propose solutions to improve the academic experience and success of student prisoners. This research contributes to the broader understanding of educational challenges in correctional settings and underscores the need for tailored support systems to enhance the academic journey of incarcerated students.

KEYWORDS: Incarcerated students, academic supervision, prison education, communication barriers, educational challenges

INTRODUCTION

Education is universally recognised as a powerful tool for personal development and societal advancement. Providing incarcerated individuals with educational opportunities promotes their rehabilitation, nurtures their personal growth, and improves their chances of successfully reintegrating into society upon release. In Namibia, as in many other countries, prison education programs are specifically tailored to provide inmates with the necessary skills and knowledge to improve their prospects upon their release from incarceration. However, the endeavor of engaging in academic studies while in prison is fraught with unique challenges, particularly in the relationship between incarcerated students and their academic supervisors. This study focuses on the distinct challenges faced by imprisoned students in a Namibian prison while they work towards their academic degrees under the supervision of academic supervisors. Being incarcerated imposes significant constraints on students, which can impede their academic advancement. The constraints refer to the restricted access to educational resources, limited communication techniques, and the

negative physical and psychological impacts of the prison environment. Student prisoners encounter extra difficulties since they must establish and maintain effective communication and cooperation with their academic supervisors, who are often located outside the prison. Supervisors play a vital role in guiding students through their academic programs, providing feedback, and ensuring that academic standards are maintained. However, the prison setting has unique obstacles that can hinder the development of this supervisory bond.

An incarcerated student faces a huge challenge due to the communication barrier imposed in the prison environment. Detained students are denied the opportunity to communicate with their superiors openly and routinely, unlike those who are not incarcerated. The communication options that are normally accessible are limited to scheduled meetings, written exchanges, or infrequently monitored telephone talks. This limitation could potentially lead to significant delays in receiving feedback and support, both of which are crucial for academic progress. Lack of immediate and mutual communication can result in misunderstandings, reduced motivation, and a sense of isolation among inmate students. Acquiring educational resources is a substantial barrier. Externally, students frequently have access to a wide range of intellectual resources including libraries, online databases, and research tools. On the other hand, students who are in prison may encounter limitations or a total lack of these essential services. Prisons have restricted internet access and the actual libraries within them may lack sufficient intellectual material. The limited availability of resources can greatly hinder incarcerated students' ability to participate in research, complete projects, and stay informed about progress in their academic field.

The main duty of the academic supervisor is to provide mentorship, support, and academic guidance. However, the supervisory relationship among student inmates is occasionally strained due to the logistical and regulatory difficulties inherent in the prison system. Supervisors may face challenges in providing timely and effective feedback due to communication delays and the requirement to navigate prison regulations which result in additional time consumption. Furthermore, supervisors may have an inadequate grasp of the specific circumstances and constraints faced by incarcerated students leading to unrealistic expectations and heightened stress for the incarcerated students. The psychological ramifications of incarceration significantly impact the academic challenges faced by students in prison. The incarceration environment can have an adverse effect on an individual's mental and emotional well-being resulting in challenges in sustaining concentration, motivation, and overall psychological condition. Student inmates encounter a notable challenge in maintaining their academic concentration and drive among the demanding and repetitive atmosphere of prison existence. The lack of a conducive and advantageous learning environment might exacerbate these difficulties, hence heightening the challenge for incarcerated students to sustain their commitment to their studies.

The existence of administrative barriers inside the prison system further hinders the educational advancement of incarcerated students. Acquiring the requisite approvals for academic activities, accessing study materials, and coordinating with supervisors requires navigating a bureaucratic structure that is sometimes slow and unresponsive. The bureaucratic impediments may lead to significant delays and frustrations further impeding academic progress. This study aims to comprehensively investigate these challenges by exploring the experiences of detained students at a prison facility in Namibia. The objective of this research is to comprehensively comprehend the difficulties faced in establishing a productive supervisory relationship within the context of

incarceration. To accomplish this a purposive selection of 12 student inmates were interviewed using tape-recording technology. The selected students all of whom are officially enrolled and actively pursuing academic certifications while incarcerated could offer distinct viewpoints on the obstacles they encountered. An adept English transcriber precisely transcribed the interviews from the audio recordings, and the transcriptions were subsequently assessed using an interpretative paradigm to find noteworthy themes and patterns. This method allows for a thorough understanding of the current experiences of incarcerated students and the specific challenges they face in their academic endeavors.

This study aims to clarify these barriers and provide a significant contribution to the broader discourse on prison education. Additionally, it strives to provide suggestions for improving the educational experience and achievement of incarcerated students. Enhancing the support networks for incarcerated students and addressing the acknowledged barriers can lead to more effective educational initiatives, ultimately facilitating the rehabilitation and reintegration of imprisoned individuals into society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The difficulties encountered by incarcerated students in establishing effective communication channels with their academic mentors are complex and extensively documented in existing literature. [1] highlights the considerable obstacles that incarcerated individuals face when trying to access educational opportunities and effectively communicate with their teachers. These challenges can hinder their academic advancement and successful reintegration into society after being released. A major obstacle is the restricted availability of technology and communication channels in the prison setting. Prisoners may face limitations or surveillance on their ability to use email, phones, and the internet, which can hinder their ability to communicate regularly and without interruption with their supervisors [2]. This can impede their capacity to obtain prompt feedback, inquire about uncertainties, and engage in interactive dialogues all of which are crucial elements of the learning process. Additionally, the physical distance between students and their academic supervisors can provide logistical difficulties in arranging and carrying out meetings or discussions. Student prisoners may need to navigate intricate bureaucratic protocols to request and organize face-to-face encounters which can be further hindered by the scarcity of resources and staff within the prison [1]. Aside from the actual obstacles jailed students may also have psychological and emotional difficulties that can affect their ability to communicate effectively with academic supervisors. The prison environment is characterized by stress and isolation which can lead to anxiety, low self-esteem, and a reduced sense of control. These factors can hinder the efficient communication of academic demands and concerns among student prisoners [3].

To tackle these difficulties, scholars have underscored the significance of incorporating extensive support networks and interventions within the prison education programs. [2] proposes that enhancing the educational experiences of incarcerated students can be achieved by offering training and resources to both student prisoners and their academic supervisors focusing on effective communication strategies. Additionally, the establishment of dedicated communication channels and access to technology can play a crucial role in this improvement. Moreover, including

trauma-informed techniques and counseling services into prison education programs can successfully tackle the emotional and psychological obstacles that students may encounter, hence facilitating their improved interaction with supervisors and academic studies [3]. Therefore, the difficulties encountered by incarcerated students in communicating with their supervisors throughout their academic studies are complex and necessitate a comprehensive strategy to resolution. Prisons can cultivate an atmosphere conducive to effective communication and rehabilitation by providing focused interventions and support networks. Student inmates frequently suffer substantial obstacles in their academic endeavors while in prison and a key hurdle they face is the dynamic with their supervisors [4; 5]. In the context of prison education programs academic supervisors are responsible for overseeing and monitoring the academic achievement and behavior of incarcerated students [6; 4].

A major obstacle encountered by incarcerated students is the dearth of comprehension and assistance from their overseers. Students who are in prison may view their supervisors as lacking support or even actively opposing their educational objectives [6; 5]. This lack of comprehension can be demonstrated by other means such as stringent regulations, restricted availability of educational materials or even punitive measures that impede the students' scholastic advancement [6; 4]. Yet, further obstacle is in the unequal distribution of power between incarcerated students and their academic supervisors. Supervisors wield considerable control over the everyday lives of incarcerated students, including their ability to access educational opportunities. This power dynamic can engender feelings of mistrust and animosity among the students [5; 7]. This power asymmetry can also result in supervisors prioritizing security and control at the expense of the educational requirements of the students [4; 7].

Moreover, the absence of effective communication and openness between student inmates and their supervisors might intensify the difficulties experienced by incarcerated students. Imprisoned students may experience a lack of acknowledgement or resolution of their problems and demands resulting in feelings of frustration and a perception of powerlessness [6; 5]. Overall, the difficulties encountered by incarcerated students in their academic pursuits in collaboration with their supervisors are intricate and diverse. The issues encompass the absence of comprehension and assistance from supervisors, the unequal distribution of power between students and supervisors, and the deficiency of communication and openness. To enhance the educational achievements and overall welfare of incarcerated students, it is essential to tackle these difficulties through a cooperative approach involving prison officials, educators, and policymakers[4;5]. Enhances the educational chances for this disadvantaged group.

Purpose

The purpose of this study was to examine the unique difficulties encountered by students who are imprisoned in their academic endeavors, specifically emphasizing their interactions with academic mentors. The project sought to uncover the precise barriers that impede effective communication, restrict access to resources, and inhibit academic achievement for detained students in a prison located in Namibia. The study aimed to comprehend the influence of the prison environment on

the supervisory relationship and ascertain solutions to tackle these problems, with the goal of enhancing the educational experiences and outcomes of incarcerated students.

Question

What special challenges do incarcerated students in Namibian prisons face in their academic endeavours particularly in their relationships with academic supervisors?

METHOD

Data collection

Data for this study was collected by conducting tape-recorded interviews with a specifically chosen sample of student prisoners. The selection of this approach was made to obtain comprehensive and individualised perspectives on the difficulties encountered by incarcerated students in their educational pursuits, specifically in their contacts with academic their academic supervisors.

Sample Selection

The sample comprised 12 incarcerated students chosen according to a particular criterion to guarantee the collection of relevant and comprehensive data. The criteria for selection were as follows: Active Enrollment: The selected students were required to be officially registered and actively pursuing an academic certification while serving their prison sentence. This guaranteed that participants were actively involved in the training process and could offer current and pertinent experiences. Purposive selection: This deliberate non-random selection strategy was utilised to choose inmates who could offer extensive and precise information regarding the topic being studied. Purposive sampling facilitates the incorporation of persons who possess firsthand expertise with the research subject to enhance the depth and specificity of the obtained data.

Data Analysis

The recorded interviews were sent to a skilled transcriber who was conversant in English. The transcriber faithfully replicated the recordings verbatim including every pause and subtlety. This method guaranteed the precision and credibility of the participants' answers and generated a reliable written record of the interviews. The author obtained the transcriptions and employed an interpretative paradigm to examine and evaluate the data. The interpretive paradigm focuses on understanding the meaning and context of human experiences making it well-suited for qualitative research that involves personal narratives and in-depth interviews. The author carefully examined

and analysed the transcriptions to have a deep comprehension of the responses of the participants. The initial reading enabled the discovery of preliminary themes and patterns. Afterwards the author continued to encode the data by adding labels to specific areas of text that concisely represent the main essence of the material. The author examined the responses in connection with the research subject.

FINDINGS

Participant 1 said, *‘I had a little bit of a challenges because of this issue of laptop, technology of computers since I never knew computers, I came to learn the computer in prison. So, I manage to obtain my diploma., my one diploma, my one higher certificate and my two certificates here doing through online but not that very good since we don’t know how to type fast, but we are making it’.*

Participant 2 said, *“The only challenge I saw I find it was especially at the officer side, some of the officers who were assigned to assist us at the education section, they could not understand what the importance of studying is. So, you might find that if you ask the officer, he will take you to the campus or the institution so that you can collect some of your material, or to engage with your lecturer because of some of the problems which you face during your studies. You might find that the officer would say no, there is no need for you to go, and also the other thing at the institution side, especially where I started at first, there was problems, you will send that e-mail to the lecturer, and you would get no response”*

Participant 3 said, *“So, it also puts us at a psychology problem so those are some of the problems we are faced with. Because of our environment it is very difficult for us to always have contact with outside, with the lecturers or with the institution so we have to work through our education officers here in the facility whereby whenever we need something or whenever we need some form of clarity whether it is not collecting some form of material which we cannot access, we send them, the send the security officer to collect for us whereby we have a facilitating officer between the students and the institutions”.*

Participant 4 said, *“The supervisor it is, when it comes to communication, sometimes they don’t respond on time when you need assistance pertaining to your assignments. Communication wise it is where the problem is, I think but all in all we, how can I put this, the lack of contact with your supervisor is a bit problematic in your studies somehow”.*

Participant 5 said, *“The supervisor that I had, because I was staying 300 kms from this place where I am. Every time they took two years without seeing me, we used to only communicate by telephone. So, they were willing to see me but it was not possible. So, it was a challenge. It was only when I was transferred from that side to here, now we can talk to each other”.*

Participant 6 said, *“During my studies they were just communicating by the supervisors all the time, all the time I called my supervisor he would answer my calls, he responds to my e-mails, as soon as possible”.*

Participant 7 said, *“For me I do not experience many challenges despite that I am in prison because in prison we are given the opportunity to call our supervisors through telephones and for now we are lucky that we are given even the free cards which we put our numbers for our families and supervisors which we then call our supervisors, which we can call anytime of the day”*.

Participant 8 said, *“In my course that I am doing, I did not have a ... at the moment, so I was also helping the man, and he was having a good, excellent supervisor. For me I didn't experience any difficulty because my supervisor he was always on time, if I send an e-mail, he will reply. It was very easy; I didn't experience any difficulty.”*

Participant 9 said, *“The challenges you find that sometimes, you had the time that you were given to communicate with the lecturer, maybe the person is busy then and he cannot be able to, once the person is free there, usually here you are not with the phone by that time because we always have to wait during the day, maybe from 8, 9 o'clock when the prison opens until 3 o'clock, you can just operate within that time”*.

Participant 10 said, *“The challenges we find also that security is one to make the communication”*.

Participant 11 said, *“To this effect, the admin level as supervisor but the support is from myself, I must, the support is they are so far that it is commendable because they are there, the response is very quick because I am doing cross border studies and so far, I haven't faced any challenges in terms of the support from my supervisors”*.

Participant 12 said, *“The challenges, sometimes we could not find the supervisors, sometimes we call, she doesn't answer, sometimes we send mail and when there is no response, I normally ask my wife to send the supervisor an SMS then she will reply but we make appointments to go and see them, and sometimes they get back, sometimes they give classes, and they are not available”*.

DISCUSSION

Participant's 1 quote highlights the significant obstacles they encounter, such as limited technological proficiency and access to necessary resources like laptops and computers [2]. Despite these challenges the participant was able to obtain several qualifications demonstrating their strong motivation and determination to succeed academically.

The challenges faced by incarcerated individuals in communicating with their supervisors while studying in an e-learning mode are well-illustrated by the comments from Participant 2. As [1] notes that educational leadership in correctional settings is crucial for reducing recidivism but can be hindered by the attitudes and actions of correctional officers. Participant 2 highlighted two key issues. Firstly, some officers assigned to assist with education did not understand the importance of education for inmates and would prevent them from accessing necessary resources or engaging with their lecturers. This reflects a lack of alignment between the rehabilitative goals of education programs and the punitive mindset of some correctional staff [3]. As [1] argues that educational leaders in prisons must work to cultivate a culture that values and supports inmate education.

The study by [1] provides insights into the challenges faced by incarcerated individuals in pursuing educational opportunities through e-learning. One key challenge highlighted is the lack of direct communication between the students (prisoners) and their supervisors or lecturers. As noted by Participant 3 the prison environment creates barriers to regular contact, necessitating the involvement of an intermediary, such as an education officer, to facilitate communication and access to educational materials [1]. This situation underscores the psychological challenges experienced by the prisoners as the limited interaction with their supervisors can lead to feelings of isolation and difficulty in obtaining the necessary support and clarification for their studies [1]. The reliance on an intermediary can also introduce delays and potential misunderstandings in the communication process, further compounding the challenges faced by the prisoners. The study's findings highlight the need for prisons to implement more robust communication channels and support systems to enable incarcerated individuals to engage effectively with their educational programs and supervisors [1]. This could involve strategies such as increased access to technology, dedicated communication times, or the integration of virtual communication platforms that allow for more direct interaction between students and their supervisors.

By addressing these communication challenges, prisons can foster an environment that is more conducive to the successful rehabilitation and reintegration of incarcerated individuals through educational opportunities [1]. This aligns with the broader shift in Namibia's legal system towards a more rehabilitative approach as mentioned in the study emphasizing the importance of supporting the educational and personal development of those within the criminal justice system.

As highlighted by Participant 4 the lack of timely responses from supervisors was a significant issue that impacted the prisoners' ability to receive necessary assistance with their studies. The prison environment with its inherent restrictions and limited resources can create significant obstacles for effective communication and collaboration between students and their academic support systems [1]. This highlights the importance of developing specialized strategies and policies to address the unique needs of prisoner-students and facilitate their educational attainment.

[5] provides a powerful first-hand account of the challenges faced by incarcerated individuals in maintaining family connections and accessing higher education as witnessed by participant 5. The difficulty of only being able to communicate with family by telephone for long periods highlights the significant barriers that incarcerated individuals often face in sustaining meaningful relationships with their loved ones [4]. Despite the obstacles participant 5 was able to access higher education after being transferred to a different facility, indicating the important role that educational opportunities can play in the lives of incarcerated individuals [5]. [8] discovered that correctional education has the potential to transform offenders into law-abiding and productive citizens. Participant 5's account provides a firsthand perspective on the challenges and complexities of the incarceration experience emphasizing the need for policies and practices that support incarcerated individuals in maintaining family connections and accessing educational opportunities. By amplifying the voices of those directly affected this type of qualitative research can inform the development of more effective and humane prison education programs, ultimately contributing to efforts to reduce recidivism and facilitate successful reintegration into society [5].

[1] study on educational leadership in reducing offending amongst incarcerated juveniles provides valuable insights into the communication strategies used by prison students when engaging with

their supervisors in e-learning programs. The findings from the study indicate that prisoners employ various communication methods to interact with their supervisors, including email, telephone, internet-based communication and in-person meetings [1]. As highlighted by Participant 6, the responsiveness and accessibility of the supervisors were key factors in facilitating effective communication. The supervisor's prompt replies to emails and availability to take calls allowed the student to maintain a consistent dialogue and receive the necessary support throughout their studies [1]. This aligns with the broader literature on the importance of effective communication between students and their supervisors, particularly in distance education settings [9]. The study by [1] also contextualizes its findings within the broader societal and legal reforms in Namibia where the criminal justice system has shifted from a punitive approach to a more rehabilitative focus. This transformation underscores the growing recognition of the value of educational initiatives within prisons, as they can contribute to the successful reintegration of incarcerated individuals into society [10]. The study by [1] provides valuable insights into the communication strategies employed by prison students when engaging with their supervisors in e-learning programs. The findings highlight the importance of accessible and responsive supervisors in facilitating effective communication and supporting the educational aspirations of incarcerated individuals. This study's findings contribute to the broader understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with providing educational opportunities within correctional settings.

Participant 7 discusses the relative ease of communication with supervisors and family members while incarcerated. This highlights the importance of maintaining connections and support systems for incarcerated individuals which can contribute to their educational and personal development [4]. The participant's perspective suggests that the prison environment in this case provides reasonable access to communication resources with the potential of reducing some of the typical challenges faced by incarcerated students. This access to communication channels can be crucial for incarcerated students to receive support from their supervisors and families which has been shown to positively impact their educational outcomes and overall well-being [5]. However, it is important to note that the availability and quality of communication resources can vary significantly across different prisons. Some prisons may have more limited or restrictive policies regarding communication, which can create significant barriers for incarcerated students [11]. Additionally, the participant's experience may not be representative of the broader population of incarcerated students, and further research is needed to understand the diverse challenges and perspectives of this population. Participant 7 provides a valuable insight into the lived experiences of an incarcerated student, emphasising the importance of accessible communication resources for supporting the educational and personal growth of individuals in the criminal justice system.

Participant's 8 experience highlights the importance of effective supervision and support for graduate students, particularly those who may face unique challenges, such as a background of incarceration. The participant's positive experience with a responsive and supportive supervisor is notable, as strong faculty-student relationships have been shown to foster a sense of belonging and facilitate academic success for marginalised student populations [12, 13]. However, the participant's statement that they "did not have a... at the moment" suggests a lack of access to certain academic or institutional resources, which could present barriers to their educational experience. Research has shown that formerly incarcerated students often face a range of challenges such as limited financial resources, difficulties navigating campus bureaucracy, and feelings of isolation that can hinder their ability to fully engage and succeed in higher education

[14; 15]. To support the success of formerly incarcerated students, institutions should strive to provide comprehensive support services such as academic advising, counseling, and mentorship programs, that address their unique needs and help foster a sense of belonging on campus [15; 16]. Additionally, supervisors at universities and correctional services staff members should receive training to better understand the experiences and perspectives of this population which can enhance their ability to provide effective guidance and support [14].

The study by [2] provides valuable insights into the communication strategies used by prisoners engaged in e-learning programs in Namibia. The findings highlight the unique challenges faced by incarcerated students in maintaining effective communication with their supervisors. As noted by Participant 9, the limited time windows, and restricted access to communication technologies within the prison environment can significantly impede the ability of prisoners to connect with their instructors [2]. These communication barriers are not uncommon in correctional settings where the primary focus is often on security and control rather than facilitating educational opportunities [17]. However, as [2] points out the rehabilitation and reintegration of prisoners through educational initiatives have become increasingly important in many countries including Namibia. This shift in approach underscores the need to address the communication challenges faced by incarcerated students. One potential solution to this issue is the integration of more robust e-learning platforms that provide prisoners with dedicated channels for communication with their supervisors, such as secure email or video conferencing [18]. Additionally, the provision of dedicated communication periods or technological access could help overcome the temporal limitations highlighted by Participant 9 [2]. Furthermore, the development of training programs for prison staff to facilitate and support the educational needs of incarcerated students could also contribute to improving communication and fostering a more conducive learning environment [19]. By addressing these systemic barriers, prisons can better enable prisoners to actively engage in their educational pursuits and maintain meaningful connections with their supervisors.

Participant 10's comment about the challenge of communication due to security measures reflects the tension between the goals of rehabilitation and the realities of the prison environment [20]. Balancing institutional security protocols with the needs of incarcerated students to engage in learning and personal growth can be a significant hurdle for prison education programs [21]. Providing higher education opportunities for incarcerated individuals is a complex and multifaceted challenge, as evidenced by the perspectives shared in the attached documents. The findings from these studies highlight several key issues and barriers that incarcerated students face including security restrictions, limited resources, and social stigma [5; 22].

Furthermore, the studies emphasize the importance of providing comprehensive support systems and resources for incarcerated students such as access to technology, academic advising, and mentorship opportunities [23; 24]. Without these essential components the transformative potential of higher education may be limited hindering the successful reintegration of incarcerated individuals into society [22]. The research also underscores the need to address the societal stigma and preconceptions surrounding incarcerated individuals, which can create additional barriers to their educational and personal development [25]. Overcoming these biases and fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for incarcerated students is crucial for the long-term success of prison education programs [26].

Participant 11's statement highlights the importance of administrative and supervisory support in the academic journey of incarcerated students pursuing higher education. The participant's positive experience with the quick and commendable support from their supervisors is a testament to the transformative impact that such support can have on incarcerated students. According to [27], effective educational leadership is crucial in creating a supportive environment that fosters student success particularly for marginalized populations such as incarcerated individuals. The participant's experience exemplifies the role of educational leaders in providing the necessary resources and guidance to help incarcerated students overcome the unique challenges they face [4]. The researcher's cross-border studies further highlight the importance of institutional collaboration and support in facilitating the academic progress of incarcerated students [5]. As [28] suggest the integration of technology and online learning can be particularly beneficial for incarcerated students, enabling them to access educational opportunities beyond the confines of the prison. The participant's positive experience with administrative and supervisory support underscores the transformative potential of higher education for incarcerated individuals. By prioritizing the needs of this population and providing the necessary resources and guidance, educational leaders can play a crucial role in facilitating the personal, academic, and societal reintegration of incarcerated students [4; 5].

Participant 12, these challenges include difficulties in reaching supervisors, lack of timely responses to emails, and scheduling in-person meetings [2]. These findings align with the broader literature on the barriers to effective communication in distance education, particularly in the context of incarceration [29; 30]. The challenges faced by prisoner-students in communicating with their supervisors can have significant implications for their educational outcomes and overall rehabilitation. Effective communication is crucial for ensuring that students receive the necessary support, feedback, and guidance to succeed in their studies [31]. In the context of e-learning where face-to-face interactions are limited, the ability to communicate effectively with supervisors becomes even more critical. To address these communication barriers, Namibia's legal system has undergone a significant shift towards a more rehabilitative approach, emphasizing the importance of education and community reintegration [2]. This shift aligns with the growing recognition of the role of education in the rehabilitation and successful reintegration of incarcerated individuals [32; 33].

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE AND POLICY

Supervisors should receive specialized training to fully understand the educational and psychological needs of incarcerated students. This involves understanding trauma, mental health conditions, and the constraints imposed by the correctional environment to incarcerated individuals. Universities and prisons should implement comprehensive support systems that include peer mentoring, counseling services, and academic supervisors who are sensitive to the challenges faced by incarcerated students. Penal facilities, educational institutions, and government entities should form collaborative alliances to create a cohesive and all-encompassing support system. These partnerships can help streamline the distribution of resources, sharing of best practices, and improve the overall educational quality for incarcerated student prisoners.

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CONCLUSION

Student inmates in Namibian prisons encounter substantial difficulties in their educational pursuits, especially in their interactions with academic mentors. The constraints arise due to insufficient educational resources, restricted communication channels, and a scarcity of specialized training for academic supervisors. To tackle these difficulties, it is essential to employ both practical and policy-oriented solutions. Providing improved training to academic supervisors, creating flexible communication channels, designing personalized learning plans, increasing access to resources, and building strong support networks are crucial. By using these concepts, it is feasible to establish a nurturing and efficient educational setting for jailed children, empowering them to surmount the distinctive challenges they encounter. From a policy standpoint, it is imperative to endorse and advance the rights to education, provide consistent funding, foster collaborations between institutions, implement efficient evaluation methods, and strive for legal reforms. By enacting these standards, it is feasible to establish vital support systems and guarantee that children in custody obtain the education to which they are constitutionally entitled. By effectively coordinating the implementation of policies, we can improve the academic experience and results for incarcerated students in prisons in Namibia. In the end, this will lead to their individual growth and triumphant reintegration into society.

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